

Solubility of Ammonium Manganese Phosphate in Water using Phosphorus-32 as a Tracer

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Effect of pH, temperature, time and free manganous ions on the solubility of ammonium manganese phosphate in water are reported.

Ammonium manganese phosphate finds many applications in industry and agriculture. Raymond¹ prepared a linear polyamide containing 100 mg/litre of manganese in the form of ammonium manganese phosphate. This polymer could be spun into a fine filament yarn and could also be drawn to give 30 denier yarn having improved dye-fastness properties. Ishihara² showed that if the surface of a soluble phosphate fertilizer is covered with ammonium manganese phosphate it becomes moisture proof. Almasy³ and co-workers have recommended it for use as a slow fertilizer. Fujiwara⁴ reported that though the efficiency of rice culture increases with heavy metal phosphate the yield is adversely affected due to toxicity of the metals. The compound has numerous other uses in pottery, pigments etc., but the data on its solubility in water and the influence of other physical factors are scanty. Wenger⁵ has reported the solubility of ammonium manganese phosphate in water at 70° and 80°, Froeseni⁵ in cold and boiling water and Otto⁵ has reported it to be insoluble in water.

In the present investigation dependence of solubility of ammonium manganese phosphate in water on time, pH, temperature and excess of manganous ions, using radioactive phosphorus isotope as tracer, is reported because of the advantages it offers over the usual gravimetric methods.

EXPERIMENTAL

Reagents: All reagents used were of BDH AnalaR or Merck (G.R.) grade. Double-distilled water was used throughout. Sodium perchlorate solution was used for maintaining ionic strength.

Buffers: Non phosphatic buffer solutions of pH 4.0, 5.0 and 6.0 were prepared by mixing appropriate amounts of M/5 potassium hydrogen phthalate and sodium hydroxide

1. T. R. White (British Nylon Spinners Ltd.), Brit. 861, 354, 1961.
2. T. Ishihara (Nissan Chemical Industries Co.), Japan 917, 1953.
3. G. Almasy, M. Gati and G. Schieber, *Magy Kem. Lapja*, 1964 19, 571.
4. A. Fujiwara, *Nippon Daigo Hiryogetsu Zasshi*, 1960, 31, 63.
5. J. W. Mellor, "A comprehensive treatise on inorganic and theoretical chemistry", Longmans, Green & Co., Vol. XII (1953), pp. 452-53.

solutions, while the buffer of pH 8.0 was prepared by mixing M/5 boric acid, potassium chloride and sodium hydroxide solutions⁶.

Preparation of ammonium manganese phosphate.—This was prepared by the method of Heints⁷. Carrier free phosphorus-32 (half life 14.3 days and maximum β energy 1.701 Mev) in the form of phosphoric acid was added to 85% phosphoric acid and the mixture was warmed with stirring for about two hours to bring about homogeneity. The acid was partially neutralised with potassium hydroxide solution and finally with ammonia. Ammonium manganese phosphate was prepared by adding manganous chloride solution containing excess of ammonium chloride in the above ammonium phosphate solution. The white precipitate of ammonium manganese phosphate thus obtained was found to have the characteristic pearl white colour which was repeatedly washed with distilled water and finally dried at 100°-105°. To check the composition of the compound, a known weight of it was taken and ignited⁷ to manganese-pyrophosphate ($Mn_2P_2O_7$) at 700° for 40 minutes. From the difference in masses in the initial and final compounds it was confirmed that the precipitated compound was ammonium manganese phosphate monohydrate ($NH_4MnPO_4 \cdot H_2O$).

Calibration : The specific activity of the ammonium manganese phosphate was determined by dissolving a known quantity of ammonium manganese phosphate in distilled water containing a few drops of nitric acid to bring about complete dissolution. The volume was made to 100 ml and various aliquots were counted with a liquid β counter. The aliquots were counted for such time that the standard deviations were always less than 10% of average count rate. The set up for counting, as shown in Fig. 1, enabled us to remove the liquid β counting tube from the instrument for thorough cleaning and changing of solutions without altering any conditions.

Solubility measurements : Excess of ammonium manganese phosphate was equilibrated with water under different conditions for several hours. The clear aliquots free from suspended material were pipetted out through Whatman No. 42 filter paper or from thoroughly centrifuged solutions and counted for activity under identical geometric conditions.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

2.38×10^4 counts/minute were found to be equivalent of one gm mole of ammonium manganese phosphate monohydrate. Average background of the beta counter was 63.4 ± 2.5 counts per minute. At the lowest reported solubility values, the standard deviation σ was as much as $\pm 50\%$ but it decreases to less than $\pm 10\%$ for the highest values of solubility. Corrections were applied for the decay of phosphorous-32 with time during the course of experiments because of short half life of the tracer.

The compound is supposed to dissociate in water according to the following equations:

6. R. E. Conway, "Electro chemical data", Elsevier Pub. Co., Amsterdam, 1952, pp. 206-207.

7. S. L. Jovanovic and B. M. Jovanovic, *Bull. Ser. Chem.* (Belgrade), 1950, 15, 107.

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For lower values of pH of the solution the concentration of H⁺ ions will be higher and hence PO₄⁻⁻⁻ ions in equation (ii) would tend to decrease due to association, phosphoric acid being a weak acid. Thus both the reactions would be forced towards the right hand side and hence higher solubility of the compound is to be expected with decreasing pH values. From Table I it is clear that the solubility increases from 1.43 × 10⁻⁴ to 7.99 × 10⁻⁴ gm moles per litre as the pH value decreases from 8.0 to 4.0. The data were obtained after 52 hours of contact time between solute and solvent, and during this period the temperature of the system was 36° ± 2°.

We have observed that by adding free Mn⁺⁺ ions in the solution the solubility of ammonium manganese phosphate decreases as is to be expected, from equation (ii) because with the addition of free Mn⁺⁺ ions the reaction should be forced towards left hand side. The results are shown in Table II from which it is observed that the solubility decreases from 5.23 × 10⁻⁴ to 1.64 × 10⁻³ gm moles/litre as the concentration of Mn⁺⁺ ions increases from 0.5 × 10⁻³ to 1.5 × 10⁻³ gm moles/litres.

FIG. 1

FIG. 2

The compound was equilibrated with distilled water for 5 days and aliquots were counted at different intervals of time. From the plot of solubility versus time (Fig. 2) it may be concluded that either initially the rate of dissolution is higher and it tends to approach equilibrium conditions after more than three days, or perhaps it transforms into some other form.

TABLE I

Solubility of ammonium manganese phosphate at various pH

pH	Solubility gm. moles/litre	Solubility product K _s
4.0	7.99 × 10 ⁻⁴	6.38 × 10 ⁻⁷
5.0	3.77 × 10 ⁻⁴	1.42 × 10 ⁻⁷
6.0	2.32 × 10 ⁻⁴	5.35 × 10 ⁻⁸
8.0	1.43 × 10 ⁻⁴	2.03 × 10 ⁻⁸

TABLE II

Influence of Mn^{++} ions on the solubility of ammonium manganese phosphate

Conc. of Mn^{++} gm moles/litre	Solubility gm moles/litre	Solubility Product K_s
6.0×10^{-4}	1.64×10^{-8}	2.67×10^{-10}
4.0×10^{-4}	2.18×10^{-8}	4.75×10^{-9}
2.0×10^{-4}	5.23×10^{-4}	2.73×10^{-7}

The results of solubility with temperature at constant ionic strength shown in Fig. 3 indicate that the solubility increases and the order of magnitude of solubility found by us are in good agreement with the data of Fresenius².

FIG. 3

The authors are grateful to Prof. J. B. Lal for help and encouragement. We also wish to thank Prof. G. L. Christie (Canadian Colombo Plan Adviser), Department of Chemistry, University of Roorkee, for the design of the remountable holder for the liquid counter.

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Received, September 9, 1966.